

WE – DREAM MODEL: INPUT TO ENHANCED SCHOOL AND COMMUNITY PARTNERSHIP IN ESTABLISHING STAKEHOLDER’S PARTICIPATION AND ENGAGEMENT IN SCHOOL PROGRAMS, PROJECTS, AND ACTIVITIES IN BUENAVISTA NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL, BUENAVISTA TINAMBAC CAMARINES SUR 4426

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ABSTRACT

The researchers employed a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative inquiry designs, to study 127 stakeholder respondents comprised of alumni, students, parents, teachers, and administrators and Barangay – LGU. Descriptive means were used to describe the data collected through validated five-point Likert questionnaires, results showed that the overall mean of stakeholder’s level of participation in school activities across aspects of school-based management was 3.93, highly collaborative. Similarly, the overall extent of engagement in programs and projects was 3.72, also highly collaborative. Overall - all participation and engagement are almost nearly engaging and empowering the highest level and degree of stakeholder engagement and participation in school programs, projects, and activities. The highest overall aspect participated by stakeholders was curriculum - instruction, with a mean score of 4.05, interpreted as high or collaborative. The lowest aspect participated in was resource management; 3.84, still reflecting a high level of collaboration. Among the respondents, teachers and administrators had the highest participation, scoring 4.26, while the barangay local government unit was the lowest, scoring 3.70, both indicating a high level of collaboration. The highest aspect engaged in by stakeholders was initiation, scoring 3.76, indicating a high level of collaboration. The lowest aspect engaged in was in planning, 3.70, reflecting a high level of collaboration. Among the respondents, teachers and administrators were the most actively engaged stakeholders, scoring 3.97, while parents were the least engaged,

scoring 3.51, both indicating a high level of collaboration. The results showed no significant difference in participation levels across aspects of school activities ($F = 1.72$, $p = 0.22$) and no significant difference in the extent of engagement in aspects of the program and project management ($F = 0.98$, $p = 0.43$). The study revealed a significant difference in respondents' participation levels in school activities ($F = 6.64$, $p = 0.004663$). Teachers were the most involved due to their direct role in education, while the barangay Local Government Unit (LGU) showed lower participation, reflecting their lesser involvement in school activities. This variation stems from the diverse roles and interests of different stakeholders. Engagement levels among respondents also exhibited a highly significant difference ($F = 30.30$, $p = .000003$). Teachers and administrators were the most engaged, while parents were the least. Stakeholders with well-defined roles, such as teachers, were more involved, whereas those with undefined roles had lower engagement. Interviews indicated that unclear responsibilities led to reduced involvement. Engagement levels varied widely based on the importance of roles, interests, and available resources within the school and community. A p-value of 0.000187, which is lower than the critical value of 0.001, indicates a significant relationship between stakeholder participation and engagement in school programs and projects. Increased stakeholder involvement leads to significantly higher engagement in school initiatives. Active participation in school activities greatly enhances their involvement in various programs and projects. The study recommends the adoption of the Dream Model. The study's interventions were highly beneficial, helping researchers solve community problems and contributing to knowledge.

Key words: *Stakeholders, Engagement, Participation, Programs, Projects, and Activities*

INTRODUCTION

The active involvement of stakeholders in school programs, projects, and activities is crucial for creating a supportive and dynamic educational environment. This study aims to develop strategies to boost engagement and participation by involving parents, teachers, community members, and local organizations in school and community projects. Engaged stakeholders help allocate resources effectively, find innovative solutions to challenges, and consistently support the school and community. This engagement ensures that resources address educational gaps and promote unity between the school and the community. However, at Buenavista National High School, stakeholder participation has remained low for the past decade, with no research or innovations undertaken to boost their engagement. The persistent low involvement from stakeholders stems from weak relationships between them and the school and vice-versa. Long-term solutions are necessary to resolve this issue, but despite this limited involvement and support, the school has attained notable academic milestones and effectively implemented tangible programs and projects.

The reviewed literature and studies presented have examined similar issues and challenges on improving stakeholder engagement and participation. Improving

stakeholder engagement, as outlined in DepEd Order No. 42, Series of 2017 of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) highlights the importance of community collaboration and professional development for teachers, emphasizing that effective teachers play a crucial role in student success and nation-building. Guzman's (2022) study showed that stakeholders are highly involved in preparing, implementing, monitoring, and evaluating the School Improvement Plan. However, this level of involvement doesn't always lead to very high school performance. De Vera (2022) found that stakeholders' participation does not affect the implementation of School-Based Management. Thus, it is recommended to revise school governance to clarify stakeholders' roles, increase their involvement in decision-making, and improve communication. Secinaro et al. (2022) highlighted the importance of e-participation tools in providing information and promoting citizen engagement. Kaku et al. (2023) stated that ignoring stakeholder concerns and satisfaction can reduce social and environmental benefits, leading to project failures. Sedmak (2021) described stakeholder engagement as how organizations interact with stakeholders: listening, collaborating, or informing them. This involves identifying, mapping, and prioritizing stakeholders to select effective communication methods and utilize resources efficiently.

There has been limited discussion on effectively integrating stakeholder engagement practices into established educational frameworks, such as the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) and School-Based Management. Addressing this gap would enhance our understanding of the role of stakeholder engagement in educational settings and offer practical guidance for educators and policymakers to optimize stakeholder involvement, thereby improving school performance and management practice.

Research Questions

This study aimed to establish the engagement and participation of stakeholders in school-initiated programs, projects, and activities as an input to enhanced community and school partnership **DREAM** model by investigating the following questions:

1. What is the participation level of stakeholders in the different school-initiated activities along a. leadership and governance; b. curriculum and learning; c. accountability and continuous improvement; and d. management of resources?
2. Is there a significant difference in the participation level of stakeholders among aspects and respondents?
3. What is the extent of involvement of stakeholders in school-based programs and projects along the phases of initiation, planning, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation and among respondents?
4. Is there a significant difference in the extent of involvement of stakeholders in school-based programs and projects along the phases of initiation, planning implementation and monitoring and evaluation and among respondents.
5. Is there significant relationship between the over – all participation of stakeholders in school-initiated activities and extent of engagement in school

programs and project management?

6. What model or framework can be adopted by the school to improve the engagement and participation of stakeholders in programs, projects, and activities?

Theoretical Framework and Model

This theoretical framework comprises concepts, theories, and principles that form a strong foundation for comprehending the research problem. These theories provide a framework that assists the researcher in presenting, analyzing, interpreting, and connecting with other theories and principles.

The study is based on **Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4): Quality Education, as cited by UNESCO (2023)**. Education promotes tolerance and helps build progressive communities. Achieving inclusive and quality education for all is essential for sustainable development. This study aims to reduce inequalities by educating and involving stakeholders in school activities and community projects.

Henri Fayol's Esprit De Corps in Management: Definition & Explanation as cited by Grimsley (2022), highlights the significance of group unity in an organization. This principle stresses the importance of stakeholders, both within the school and the community, working together cohesively. School managers play a vital role in promoting morale and effective communication. Esprit de corps fosters a culture of trust and understanding among individuals.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

The Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) (2017) were utilized in this study to advance quality learning and teaching with the support of stakeholders. The PPST delineates seven domains, with this study concentrating on Domain 6: Community Linkages and Professional Engagement. Moreover, by engaging in Domain 6, we also improve our competencies within Domain 7: Personal Growth and Professional Development.

This study aims to evaluate the level of participation and extent of engagement of the stakeholders and linkages of Buenavista National High School in school programs, projects, and activities (PPA's) this AY 2023.

The study is supported by **Participative Leadership Theory and Decision-Making Style, as cited by Eleanor Myers (2023)**. Participative leadership encourages democratic decision-making and fosters creativity among team members. It involves group members sharing their ideas and opinions when decisions are made. This leadership style promotes greater involvement in organizational activities compared to other styles. While it is less common in the corporate world, certain professions may find it beneficial to adopt participative leadership.

Design Thinking Model

The researcher utilized the design thinking approach to answer the needs and problems of the adopted community. **Dam and Siang (2024)**, defined design thinking as a systematic process comprising five key stages: empathize, define, ideate, prototype, and test. This method centers on understanding users' needs and experiences, challenging assumptions, and refining problems to develop innovative and effective solutions.

Phase 1: Empathizing. This stage is crucial for understanding the challenges and needs of the community. By empathizing with stakeholders, the researchers gained firsthand insights into the community's current situation.

Phase 2: Defining stage. Buenavista National High School has faced a decade-long challenge of low stakeholder participation and engagement in its programs, projects, and activities, stemming from poor relationships between stakeholders and the school. This problem requires a solution.

Phase 3: Ideation: This phase involved a creative process where designers brainstormed ideas to develop solutions. Motivational activities, like fun-day events, were used to encourage stakeholder participation and recommended in the school activities, alongside seeking support from community linkages and donors.

Phase 4: Creating a Prototype: The fourth stage is creating a prototype or model that will identify the best solutions for the identified problems. Study and innovation are unique by designing a model out of the existing models in literature and studies; the enhancement of community and school partnership model is a proposed

innovation of the study aimed at improving the level of participation and engagement of stakeholders in programs, projects, and activities in school (PPA's).

Phase 5: Testing the prototype: This phase is focused on testing the Dream Model to assess its effectiveness in improving stakeholder participation and resource management within schools.

Figure 2: Design Thinking

Model.

Conceptual Framework

This study was guided by the conceptual framework in **figure 3**. The schematic diagram illustrates the development of enhanced community and school partnership **DREAM** model. The arrow connecting the boxes showed the correlation of the aspects and the variables which the researchers' studied and examined. The first box showed the variables of the stakeholder's level of participation in school activities along leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement and management of resources. The second box presented the variables on the extent of engagement of stakeholders in school programs and projects along the phases of initiation, planning, implementation and monitoring and evaluation.

To achieve the research goals and objectives along with the proposed output, the level of participation of stakeholders in school activities and the extent of engagement in programs and projects were assessed. Likewise, the significant differences in the participation level and engagement in programs and projects among aspects and respondents were tested. Furthermore, the significant relationship between the participation level of stakeholders in the different school-initiated activities along a. Leadership and governance; b. curriculum and learning; c. accountability and continuous improvement; and d. management of resources and the extent of involvement of stakeholders in programs and projects along the phases of a. initiation; b. planning; c. implementation; d. monitoring and evaluation was also determined and established.

The innovation identified as a solution to the needs and problems of the community is the We-Dream Project: Develop, Reinforce, Empower, Affirm, and Motivate Stakeholders Engagement and Participation in the Schools' Program Projects and Activities. The output is an enhanced community and school partnership DREAM model. Study and innovation are unique by designing a model out of the existing models in literature and studies; the adopted e-participation tools using digital and electronic media platforms is a proposed innovation of the study aimed at improving the level of participation and engagement of stakeholders in programs, projects, and activities in school.

The program will help the school build a stable support system of stakeholders in the community; the successful implementation of the program will improve students' academic performance and increase the participation of parents in school programs, projects, and activities. The project aims to help reduce inequalities and empower people in the community to live a sustainable life, this is a vital tool in breaking the cycle of poverty and in developing a progressive community.

Figure 3: Conceptual Framework

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research employed a mixed methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis. The study used descriptive, comparative, and relational methods to address the research questions. First, the study detailed the level of stakeholders' participation in school activities, examining dimensions such as leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability, continuous improvement, and resource management. Second, it described the degree of

stakeholder engagement in programs and projects across different phases: initiation, planning, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation. The study also identified differences in stakeholder engagement across various aspects and among different respondent groups. Furthermore, the research explored significant relationships between stakeholder participation levels in different school-led activities and their degree of involvement in programs and projects. Specifically, it investigated participation in a) Leadership and governance, b) Curriculum and instruction, c) Accountability and continuous improvement, and d) Resource management. The study also examined involvement in: a) Initiation, b) Planning, c) Implementation, and d) Monitoring and evaluation. By integrating these various dimensions, the study provided a comprehensive analysis of stakeholder participation and engagement in school activities and programs.

Methods & Procedures

The research employed a quantitative survey approach using a questionnaire validated by experts. The quantitative findings were supported and validated by a qualitative generic inquiry through focus group discussions with participants selected via purposive sampling. The survey questionnaire was administered personally to the 127 stakeholders of Buenavista National High School, including alumna, students, teachers, administrators, parents, and members of the Barangay Council (local government unit). Before the final data collection, the survey questionnaire was pilot tested with selected respondents to evaluate its validity and enhance the quality of the material. This pilot testing ensured the instrument was reliable and effective for the final data collection.

The study employed a self-designed questionnaire, validated by experts, offered in both English and Bicol dialects. The questionnaire comprised three sections: the respondent's profile; aspects concerning levels of involvement in leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability, continuous improvement, and monitoring and evaluation; and statements concerning stakeholder engagement throughout the phases of initiation, planning, implementation, and monitoring and evaluation. Researchers employed a back-translation method assisted by experts to translate the questionnaire between English and Bicol dialects.

The Bicol questionnaire was for parents and respondents who preferred the Bicol dialect. The scale utilized to measure stakeholder participation in school activities is a 5- point Likert scale, ranging from (1) "very low" to (5) "very high" or empowering, encompassing three (3) statements. These statements concerning the degree of participation were in line with the school-based management assessment tool. This tool evaluates stakeholder engagement in school activities, specifically focusing on leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement, and resource management. The scale provides a structured way to assess stakeholders' perceptions of their involvement, ranging from minimal information provision to significant empowerment within these domains.

The degree of engagement of stakeholders was determined by a 5-point Likert

scale, ranging from (1) "very low" or informing to (5) "very high" or engaging, consisting of three (3) statements. These statements concerning the level of participation in programs and projects are the phases of the project life cycle of project management.

Respondents Profile

The distribution of stakeholders' respondents in is as follows: 22 alumni (17.32%), 42 students (33.07%), 33 parents or guardians (25.98%), 20 members of administration, faculty, and staff (15.75%), and 10 members of the Barangay Council – Local Government Unit (LGU) (7.87%). Students make up the largest group of respondents, while the Barangay Council – LGU has the fewest respondents. The study aimed to include a sample of 100 respondents, as recommended by **Frankel and Wallen (2019)**, for descriptive research. However, to enhance the ability to detect significant differences using analysis of variance, the sample size was increased to 127 respondents from various stakeholder groups within the school. This exceeds the minimum sample size suggested by Frankel and Wallen. The sample size was calculated by dividing the respondent population by the total population size and multiplying by 100, determining the total number of respondents for the study.

$$\text{Formula} = \frac{RPS (n)}{N}$$

Where:

RPS – are the respondents. *N* – Total Population.

n – is constant which is equals to 100.

Locale and Population

The locale of the study is Buenavista National High School, located in Buenavista, Tinambac, Camarines Sur. This secondary school, situated in the fourth district of the Division of Camarines Sur, is classified as a medium school with a total enrollment of 423 students and less than 1,000 stakeholders. Most of the school community, comprising almost 75% of the population, consists of fisherfolk and farmers. Fishermen in this area depend on the sea for their livelihood, while farmers rely on rainfall due to the absence of a functional irrigation system. Consequently, life is challenging for many families of students. Buenavista is a coastal area with a land area of 1,059 hectares, located approximately 8 kilometers from the town proper. Positioned in the southern part of Tinambac, the community's primary sources of livelihood are coconut farming and fishing. The name "Buenavista" was given by Spanish missionaries during the Spanish era, meaning "good view" or "good sight," which aptly describes the area's scenic surroundings (Barangay Demographic Profile, 2023).

RESULTS

1. LEVEL OF PARTICIPATION IN SCHOOL INITIATED ACTIVITIES.

Results showed that the overall mean of stakeholder's level of participation in school activities across aspects of school-based management was 3.93, highly collaborative.

The highest overall aspect participated by stakeholders was curriculum - instruction, with a mean score of 4.05, interpreted as high or collaborative. The lowest aspect participated in was resource management; 3.84, still reflecting a high level of collaboration. Among the respondents, teachers and administrators had the highest participation, scoring 4.26, while the barangay local government unit was the lowest, scoring 3.70, both indicating a high level of collaboration.

2. SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCES ON THE LEVEL OF PARTICIPATION AMONG ASPECTS AND RESPONDENTS.

The results showed no significant difference in participation levels across aspects of school activities ($F = 1.72$, $p = 0.22$) but there was significant difference in respondents' participation levels in school activities ($F = 6.64$, $p = 0.004663$)

3. EXTENT OF ENGAGEMENT IN SCHOOL PROGRAMS AND PROJECTS.

The overall extent of engagement in programs and projects was 3.72, also highly collaborative. The highest aspect engaged in by stakeholders was initiation, scoring 3.76, indicating a high level of collaboration. The lowest aspect engaged in was in planning, 3.70, reflecting a high level of collaboration. Among the respondents, teachers and administrators were the most actively engaged stakeholders, scoring 3.97, while parents were the least engaged, scoring 3.51, both indicating a high level of collaboration.

4. SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCES ON THE EXTENT OF ENGAGEMENT AMONG ASPECTS AND RESPONDENTS.

There was no significant difference in the extent of engagement in aspects of the program and project management ($F = 0.98$, $p = 0.43$). However, engagement levels among respondents also exhibited a very high significant difference ($F = 30.30$, $p = .000003$).

Teachers and administrators were the most engaged, while parents were the least. Stakeholders with well-defined roles, such as teachers, were more involved, whereas those with undefined roles had lower engagement. Interviews indicated that unclear responsibilities led to reduced involvement. Engagement levels varied widely based on the importance of roles, interests, and available resources within the school

and community.

5. SIGNIFICANT RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE OVER – ALL PARTICIPATION OF STAKEHOLDERS IN SCHOOL INITIATED ACTIVITIES AND EXTENT OF ENGAGEMENT IN SCHOOL PROGRAMS AND PROJECT MANAGEMENT.

A p-value of 0.000187, which is lower than the critical value of 0.001, indicates a significant relationship between stakeholder participation and engagement in school programs and projects. Increased stakeholder involvement leads to significantly higher engagement in school initiatives. Active participation in school activities greatly enhances their involvement in various programs and projects.

6. PROPOSED DREAM MODEL.

The Dream model was developed by the researchers to foster greater participation and involvement of stakeholders in school programs, projects, and activities. The prototype developed through the research findings and recommendations aims to bridge the gap in stakeholder engagement along resource management planning, low participation of LGU – Barangay in school-initiated activities and parents, and engagement in project management. The Dream program provides a structured and innovative model outlined in the action plan to enhance participation, improve resource allocation, and achieve better educational outcomes. The DREAM action plan, aligned with the school improvement plan, can be proposed for implementation with budget through approval from the school head and the school planning and review team.

This model aims to enhance stakeholder involvement in resource inventories and the development of resource programs, thereby improving the allocation and mobilization of school resources to meet educational goals. By addressing the needs related to resource allocation and securing additional resources through the DREAM program, the school can effectively resolve the other issues and needs identified in the study.

DISCUSSION

Conclusion 1

Overall - all participation is almost nearly empowering the highest level and degree of participation in school-initiated activities. Stakeholders actively collaborate and participate in school activities focused on school-based management practices. Their deep involvement signifies a strong partnership between decision-makers and stakeholders, highlighting shared responsibility and collaborative problem-solving. They contribute their time, expertise, and resources to support the school's goals, showing a shared commitment to excellence and quality education.

Stakeholders actively shape the school's curriculum and teaching methods,

prioritizing quality education to provide the best learning experience for students. Their collaboration reflects a shared commitment to meeting the needs of students, teachers, and the community. They regularly review and update the curriculum, integrate new teaching methods, and adapt strategies to meet evolving standards and student needs.

Stakeholders are less engaged in managing school resources, conducting inventories, and developing programs. Despite this, resource management still perceives significant role in stakeholders participation. Challenges include competing priorities, limited awareness, lack of resources or expertise, and communication barriers. Addressing these issues requires raising awareness, providing resources and expertise, improving communication, and emphasizing the importance of resource management to enhance collaboration and support the school's goals.

Teachers and administrators are deeply involved in school-initiated activities, demonstrating strong teamwork and cooperation. They collaborate on various school-initiated activities, showing a shared commitment to its mission and goals. Their effective collaboration suggests participation in decision-making and implementing programs to enhance the school's performance. This teamwork is crucial for fostering a supportive and cohesive school environment where everyone works efficiently together. Through their joint efforts, teachers and administrators significantly contribute to positive outcomes in the school community, including supporting student achievement, improving educational experiences, and advancing the school's overall mission.

The results showed that barangay LGUs (Local Government Units) had the least involvement in school-initiated activities. Several factors contribute to this limited participation: resource constraints such as budget limitations and competing priorities, a communication gap between schools and LGUs leading to low awareness of their role, differences in policy priorities between LGUs and the education sector, and community dynamics affecting local support for education and adherence to cultural norms. Overcoming these challenges involves improving communication, building LGU capacity, aligning policy objectives, and promoting community engagement in education initiatives.

Conclusion 2

The results show no significant difference in stakeholder participation across various aspects. Respondents have similar perceptions and responses regarding participation in school activities. This consistency is due to the Department of Education's standardized procedures for evaluating school-based management dimensions: leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, continuous improvement and accountability, and resource management. These procedures ensure that stakeholders perceive and respond to participation opportunities in the same way.

However, results indicate a highly significant difference in participation levels among respondents. Teachers who play a central role in teaching and learning exhibit

the highest participation levels, as indicated by their highest mean score. In contrast, the barangay LGU, the local government unit, has the lowest participation level among stakeholders, as shown by their lowest mean score, indicating their limited involvement in school activities. LGUs have less direct engagement in school affairs, leading to less active participation. These differences stem from stakeholders' varied interests, motivation, readiness to participate, and availability of resources.

Conclusion 3

Overall - engagement is almost nearly engaging the highest degree of stakeholder engagement in school programs and projects. Stakeholders demonstrate highly collaborative engagement across all aspects of project management. The finding indicates active collaboration among the school's stakeholders, pooling their efforts, resources, and expertise in managing programs and projects. This teamwork reflects a strong commitment and positive synergy in enhancing stakeholder engagement within the school. In conclusion, stakeholders have significantly contributed to cultivating a productive and supportive learning environment through their collaborative efforts and positive changes.

Stakeholders were deeply engaged in project initiation, actively initiating new projects or initiatives. They play a crucial role in conducting needs analyses to identify and allocate essential resources such as budget, personnel, and materials for project execution. Recognizing the importance of addressing challenges and seizing opportunities, stakeholders take the lead in launching new projects. Emphasizing project initiation underscores their innovative contributions to project management.

Planning exhibits the lowest level of stakeholder engagement, underscoring a need for improvement. Stakeholders participate less in planning than in project initiation and other management phases, primarily due to limited familiarity, skills, knowledge, and resources. Interviews and group discussions with stakeholders highlight challenges they encounter in engaging in school planning activities, stemming from unfamiliarity with processes, reluctance to attend consultative meetings, lack of confidence, and unclear roles and responsibilities. Stakeholders are keen to be actively involved in planning from initiation to completion. Enhancing stakeholder participation in planning programs and projects is essential for effective project management.

Teachers and administrators at Buenavista National High School are deeply immersed in school-initiated programs and projects, actively participating in daily operations and demonstrating a profound understanding of student needs and challenges. Their interactions with students and other stakeholders provide valuable insights that help identify beneficial programs and projects for enhancing the school's performance. Teachers cultivate strong relationships with students, parents, and administrators, promoting effective collaboration and support for these initiatives. Their dedicated involvement and collaborative efforts in school-initiated programs and projects foster positive changes that lead to school improvement.

Parents are the least involved stakeholders in school-initiated programs and projects. Despite this, they exhibit a high level of collaborative engagement, typically participating by attending meetings and volunteering for school activities. In-depth interviews reveal that parents prioritize their jobs and support their families. Factors contributing to their limited engagement include a lack of confidence and resources such as time, money, skills, and knowledge. Parental responsibilities, such as running errands or caring for younger children, further constrain their availability. Communication gaps between school and parents also impact their involvement, with parents sometimes feeling their contributions are undervalued compared to those of teachers or administrators. Despite their lower level of engagement, parents' participation remains significant.

Conclusion 4

The result showed that there was no significant difference in stakeholder engagement across different aspects of programs and projects. Therefore, efforts to enhance engagement do not need to focus on specific aspects, as engagement is uniform across all areas. Moreover, it can be concluded that the result is due to the uniformity of policy implementation regarding program and project implementations within the Department of Education.

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) results revealed a highly significant difference in the extent of engagement among respondents. Stakeholders showed varying levels of involvement in school programs and projects based on the tasks and duties they fulfil within the school environment.

Teachers demonstrated the highest engagement, as indicated by the highest mean and rank, while parents exhibited the lowest engagement, reflected by the lowest mean score and rank. When stakeholders have significant roles and responsibilities, such as teachers who are directly involved in teaching and managing classrooms, they tend to show higher levels of engagement. This increased involvement is often due to the necessity of active participation and interaction with school programs and projects.

Conversely, stakeholders with lesser-defined roles or responsibilities tend to be less engaged. Their engagement levels are generally lower when roles and responsibilities are unclear. The level of engagement can thus vary widely among stakeholders, often aligning with the scope and importance of their roles within the school community.

Conclusion 5

When stakeholders are more involved in school activities, their engagement in school programs and projects increases significantly. Active participation in school activities strongly influences their involvement in various programs and projects. Stakeholders who feel connected to the school community are more likely to support its initiatives with their time, resources, and ideas. Encouraging participation in activities and project engagement fosters stable relationships and improves outcomes for the

school and community.

Conclusion 6

The study recommends the adoption of the Dream Model. The Dream is a model developed by the researchers to foster greater participation and involvement of stakeholders in school programs, projects, and activities. The prototype developed through the research findings and recommendations aims to bridge the gap in stakeholder engagement along resource management planning, low participation of LGU – Barangay in school-initiated activities and parents, and engagement in project management. The Dream program provides a structured and innovative model outlined in the action plan to enhance participation, improve resource allocation, and achieve better educational outcomes. The DREAM action plan, aligned with the school improvement plan, can be proposed for implementation with budget through approval from the school head and the school planning and review team.

Recommendations:

The school should offer training sessions on resource management techniques, budgeting, and program development to empower stakeholders to contribute effectively. Likewise, it is essential to implement a system for evaluating resource management to identify strengths and areas for improvement to make necessary adjustments. These strategies should actively engage stakeholders through meetings, surveys, focus groups, and workshops. Likewise, the study suggests training on livelihood and income-generating projects in collaboration with linkages and government agencies that are experts in these fields. This training aims to equip stakeholders with the necessary skills to secure funds and additional resources for the school and community. The model seeks to increase stakeholder involvement in resource inventories and the development of resource programs, thereby improving the allocation and mobilization of school resources to meet educational goals. By addressing needs related to resource allocation and securing additional resources through the DREAM program, the school can effectively resolve other issues and needs identified in the study.

Improving Local Government Units (LGUs) participation in school activities can enhance community support and resources for educational programs. Schools should organize events that showcase student talents and achievements to demonstrate the value of LGU support. Formalizing the relationship between schools and LGUs through MOUs is essential, outlining mutual commitments and specific activities for collaboration. Schools should involve LGU representatives in planning and organizing activities and create joint committees with school staff, LGU members, parents, and community leaders for collaborative decision-making. Regular meetings between school administrators and LGU representatives are crucial. Additionally, schools should use social media and newsletters to inform the community about upcoming activities and their importance. Publicly acknowledging LGU contributions through award ceremonies and social media can encourage continued participation.

Improving stakeholder engagement in planning is crucial for ensuring successful sustainable programs and projects in schools. Implementing innovative strategies fosters an inclusive, responsive, and engaging planning environment with stakeholders, leading to more successful outcomes. Planning with stakeholders involved them from initiation to completion, establishing transparent communication channels, providing regular progress updates, and gathering feedback through meetings, focus group discussions, and surveys. Building strong, personal relationships with stakeholders, acknowledging their contributions, and ensuring they have the necessary resources and support are also vital. Offering flexible engagement options, providing incentives for participation, and demonstrating the tangible impact of their involvement further enhance engagement. Moreover, promoting collaboration cultivates harmony in the community and strengthens their engagement in school programs and projects.

The study suggests ways to increase parental involvement in school programs and projects. These include hosting quarterly parent-teacher meetings and organizing activities that require parental participation, such as fun day events and mentoring sessions through the general parents' teacher's association. These sessions allow parents to discuss reasons for their limited engagement in programs and projects. There is a critical need for dialogue and meaningful discussions to address problems and issues in program and project management. Parents should actively participate in consultative meetings and contribute to the planning process rather than just agreeing to plans without their input. Additionally, parents stress the importance of transparency and accountability in all school programs and projects, supported by clear documentation and evidence. Furthermore, it's a must to keep parents informed about school events and their child's progress through newsletters, emails, and mobile apps. Offering volunteer opportunities within the school for parents to help in classrooms or activities can also increase engagement. Using technology for virtual meetings and providing online resources accessible to parents is beneficial. Finally, recognizing parental involvement through awards or acknowledgments can strengthen the partnership between parents and educators. Interviews revealed that parents prefer to participate in training, mentoring, and livelihood programs. These efforts collectively enhance collaboration between parents and educators to improve student outcomes and a more supportive learning environment.

The study recommends the adoption of the Dream Model. The model provides motivational activities and strategies through the action plan to enhance participation and engagement in programs projects and activities specifically on resource management, planning, and low participation of barangay – LGU on school activities and parent's engagement in school programs and project management. The **DREAM** model aims to enhance stakeholder involvement in resource inventory and program development, to improve the allocation and utilization of school resources to meet educational goals. By addressing resource needs and securing additional resources through the **DREAM** program, the school can effectively resolve other issues identified in the study.

The model emphasizes the importance of focusing on what the school can offer

stakeholders rather than solely on what stakeholders can contribute to the school and community. This shift in focus aims to enhance the engagement and presence of stakeholders, making their involvement more meaningful and beneficial.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers affirm that the process followed in conducting this study was duly approved by, and carried out with the consent of, the relevant departments involved. The anonymity of all respondents was safeguarded throughout the study, and participants were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence.

The researcher also ensures that no harm was caused to any respondents during the study, and that there was no conflict of interest in the research process. Furthermore, strict adherence to academic integrity was maintained, with plagiarism being actively avoided, and the manuscript reviewed by subject-matter experts.

Additionally, the researchers confirm that there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings, and that the results were used solely for research purposes.

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REFERENCES

- Barangay Demographic Profile. (2023). Profile of Buenavista. Retrieved from <http://bdp.bgas-phil.net/pdf/bdp/194>
- Dam, R. F., & Siang, T. Y. (2024). What is design thinking and why is it so popular. Interaction Design Foundation. Retrieved from <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/article/what-is-design-thinking-and-why-is-it-so-popular>
- De Vera, V. (2022). Stakeholders' participation and its correlation with the implementation of school-based management of Bambang East Elementary School. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 11(11), 101–106.
- Fraenkel, J. R., & Wallen, N. E. (2019). *How to design and evaluate research in education* (7th ed.). McGraw Hill Education.
- Grimsley, S. (2022). Henri Fayol's esprit de corps in management: Definition & explanation. Study.com. Retrieved from <https://study.com/academy/lesson/esprit-de-corps-in-management-definition-lesson-quiz.html>
- Guzman, J. (2022). Stakeholders' participation in school improvement plans and school performance of secondary schools. *International Journal of Arts, Sciences and Education*, 3(July Special Issue), 51–66. Retrieved from <https://ijase.org/index.php/ijase/article/view/159>
- Kaku, P. M., Zhu, H., & Fangninou, F. F. (2023). Evaluation of the EIA process in Zanzibar: The participation of stakeholders in public and private projects. *Environment, Development & Sustainability*, 25(8), 7461–7481. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-022-02334-2>
- Myers, E. (2023). Participative leadership theory and decision-making style. *International Journal of Public Administration*, 45(9), 708-725.
- Secinaro, A., et al. (2022). Does citizen involvement feed on digital platforms? *Journal of Public Administration*, 17(4), 505-520. Retrieved from <https://www.smestrategy.net/blog/stakeholder-engagement-management-for-strategic-planning>
- Sedmak, J. (2021). How do you use the Gardner model to identify and prioritize your stakeholders? *Simply Psychology*. Retrieved from <https://www.simplypsychology.org/participative-leadership.html>